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PODCAST PRODUCTION: STEP-BY-STEP

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CAMERA SETUP

Use three cameras: one for a wide shot and two for over-the-shoulder shots.

Position your wide-shot camera in front of the podcast hosts, capturing the entire set.

Place the over-the-shoulder cameras behind each host, pointing at their profiles.

CAMERA SETTINGS

ISO: Set all cameras to ISO 400 for optimal lighting conditions.

APERTURE: Use a wide aperture, around f/2.8, to achieve a shallow

depth of field, keeping your hosts in focus while blurring the background.

SHUTTER SPEED: Adjust your shutter speed according to your frame rate for natural motion blur

(E.G., 1/50 FOR 24 FRAMES PER SECOND).

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MICROPHONE SETUP

Quality audio is crucial for your podcast. We'll use two microphones for this setup.

Place one microphone in front of each podcast host, ensuring they are at the ideal speaking distance. These microphones should be out of the camera's frame but close enough for clear audio.

MICROPHONE SETTINGS

Adjust your microphone settings for balanced audio. Ensure they're connected to your recording equipment and tested for clarity before recording.

Headphones are essential for monitoring audio quality during the podcast recording. Continuously monitor the audio levels through headphones to ensure clear and balanced sound.

CAMERA OPERATION

Start all cameras simultaneously. Make sure they are recording in the highest quality available. Keep an eye on the framing and focus throughout the recording.

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POST-PRODUCTION

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OPEN ADOBE PREMIERE PRO ON YOUR COMPUTER.

Import Footage: Go to the "File" menu, select "Import," and navigate to the folder containing your podcast footage. Select all the video clips you want to use and click "Import."

Create New Project: Click on "New Project" and specify the project settings such as resolution, frame rate, and scratch disk location. Click "OK."

Place Videos in the Timeline: Drag and drop your video clips onto the timeline in the order you want them to appear.

SYNCHRONIZE WITH MICROPHONE AUDIO

Import Microphone Audio: In the Project panel, import the audio files from your microphones.

Select both the video clip and the corresponding microphone audio clip, right-click, and choose "Synchronize." Premiere Pro will match the audio and video based on their timestamps.

NEST THE SEQUENCE

Right-click on your timeline and select "Nest." This step is optional but can help you manage multiple clips more efficiently.

ENABLE MULTI-CAM EDITING

Right-click on the nested sequence in the Project panel and select "Create Multi-Camera Source Sequence." This will open the Multi-Camera Sequence dialog box.

Edit with Multi-Cam: Double-click on the Multi-Camera Sequence to open it in the timeline. Now, you can start editing your podcast by switching between camera angles in real-time by pressing the numbers 1, 2, and 3 on your keyboard. Use "C" and "V" to cut and switch between angles seamlessly.

EXPORT YOUR PROJECT

Once you've finished editing, go to the "File" menu, select "Export," and choose the format and settings that match your requirements. Specify the destination folder and click "Export."